
Correlation between births in Linz (2006 - 2016) and (healthy) life expectancy of Europeans at birth by sex

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

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Project abstract:

This experiment shows correlation between births in Linz in the years of 2006 – 2016 and the average life expectancy and healthy life expectancy of people that are born in Europe in the corresponding years (2006 – 2016). By conducting this experiment, a link between births and trends of life expectancy, especially the healthy life expectancy can be established.

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1. Data summary

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

This experiment shows correlation between births in Linz in the years of 2006 – 2016 and the average life expectancy and healthy life expectancy of people that are born in Europe in the corresponding years (2006 – 2016). By conducting this experiment, a link between births and trends of life expectancy, especially the healthy life expectancy can be established.

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

It's an interesting topic with no similar projects regarding this topic and I wanted to see if there exist any correlations between the datasets.

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

The main output that is generated by the experiment are different plots, that show the relation and correlation between the different input-datasets. These are generated in form of PNG-images. Furthermore, the underlying dataset (result of merging and transforming the input-datasets), which is used for the plots, is also provided as a CSV-file.

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

The data, concerning (healthy) life expectancy at birth by sex, consists of a numeric value for

- life expectancy male
- life expectancy female
- (healthy) life expectancy male
- (healthy) life expectancy female

for each year ranging from 2006 to 2016.

The data, concerning total registered births in Linz, consists of numeric values for births (separated in age-groups, which are summed up in the experiment) for each year ranging from 2006 to 2016. These separate numeric values are then combined in a single dataset for further use.

Specify the origin of the data

The data is downloaded from two different repositories. The first one is <https://www.data.gv.at>, and the second one is <http://data.europa.eu/cuodp/en/home>.

State the expected size of the data (if known)

The size of the correlation plots are expected to be around 50-60KB, the main plot around 150KB and the size of the underlying data for the plots in CSV-format around 2KB.

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The data that is generated by the experiment can be used by other datascientists for forecasting and establishing trends.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata [FAIR data]

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The datasets are described in the data-summary. No further metadata is stored.

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

The project is publicly available on zenodo.org, found by the DOI [10.5281/zenodo.2648554](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2648554).

Outline naming conventions used

The naming convention for the data-files and output-files was chosen to be as descriptive of the content as possible, so that it is definite which file contains which data or plots.

Outline the approach towards search keyword

The keywords are chosen to encompass the topic. Keyword are e.g. "births", "life expectance", "healthy life expectance", aswell as areal descriptions.

Outline the approach for clear versioning

Versioning is handled via Github.

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

DCMI metadata (dublin core schema) can be used as a standard for metadata-creation.

2.2 Making data openly accessible [FAIR data]

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

All data that is used as input or generated as output by this project is made publicly available on Zenodo. The source-code that is used to transform data and produce the output is also made publicly available on Zenodo.

Specify how the data will be made available

All the data regarding this project is made publicly available on the Zenodo-platform.

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The only necessary software tool is RStudio and the programming language R. The project includes a readme.txt that has a step-by-step guide on how to reproduce the output with the given input.

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

All associated data can be found on the platform Zenodo using the unique identifier [10.5281/zenodo.2648554](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2648554) (DOI).

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

The project is licensed with the MIT standard. Anyone can access and download the project files.

2.3 Making data interoperable [FAIR data]

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

The project produces output in form of a CSV, with text and numeric values. This format is one of the most widely used one and any other project should be able to interoperate.

The project will follow the DCMI metadata vocabulary, and keep the data vocabularies overseable and alike (if new versions of the project will be made in the future).

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

The standard vocabulary is documented (regarding the more unusual terms) within the source files, therefore providing future datascientists that want to work with the produced output of the project with clear explanations on what the data is.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses) [FAIR data]

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

For this project, the MIT License is used to permit the widest reuse possible.

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

The data will be made available as soon as possible. The data should be accessible already using the Zenodo-platform. There is not going to be any data-embargo.

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

Since the produced data is both, accessible as CSV (raw data), aswell as PNG-images, it opens up the reusability of the produced data for just referencing (PNG) the project/correlation between the topics and further data-transformation (raw data).

Describe data quality assurance processes

The input data was very compact, therefore manual checks were used to assure quality.

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

Since the data is from a capsulated time-frame (2006 - 2016), it is already bygone and not uptodate. Therefore as reference material it can be use for the coming decades, or as long as it makes sense to reference the data in future projects. The data will be accessible on Zenodo until it's being archived (no announced time for that at the moment).

3. Allocation of resources

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

There were no costs for making the data FAIR. The raw input data is from free repositories, the only contributor is the author himself and making the project with all associated data publicly available is done through the Zenodo-platform, which is free aswell.

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

The only contributor to this project is the author himself, Markus Drechsel. No further identification of responsibilities is necessary.

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

Using Zenodo, there are no future costs, even regarding long term preservation. The potential value of long term preservation is, that with publishing this project, all the associated data is preserved in this project aswell. So even when the open-source repositories delete the used input-data, it will still be available through this project.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

Since the data is uploaded and preserved on the Zenodo-platform, storage and transfer of sensitive data is guaranteed by Zenodo-standards.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

The input and output data of this project are completely anonymized. There is no unethical act.

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

No others.